

Initial Design of the Multifunction Bioeconomy Tool

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² PU=Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), CI=Classified

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1 Introduction

RESIST activities aim to focus on solutions to improve overall adaptation to climate change. The intended responses are involved within the environmental, socioeconomic and agroforestry scope. European Union defined Bioeconomy as one of the most important sectors to contribute to Climate Change fight and adaptation, but with needs of adaptation and mitigation actions.

The RESIST project defined a framework of challenges for the development of the bioeconomy tool, as shown in figure 1.1, take into account the free dimension (air, water and soil) that will permit to performance a software tool support with interface for users for modulation scenarios.

Framework of the challenges Bioeconomy Tool

Figure 1.1 Framework of the Bioeconomy tool and the twinning potential dimensions (air, water and soil).

For a better understanding of the Tool, in figure 1.2 there is a diagram of the essential principles of its performance and high efficiency.

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Figure 1.2 Schematic representation of the design of the proposed Multifunction Bioeconomy Tool.

For the Resist project we defined the next goals, G:

G1. Three important dimensions of the climate change with impact in natural resources: “AIR”, “LAND” and “WATER”.

G2. Development of a new bioeconomy tool with 4 level functions, LF, in response to climate change:

- o LF1. Circular;
- o LF2. Sustainable;
- o LF3. Resilient; and
- o LF4. Safe.

G3. A Portuguese pilot focused on agroforestry, socioeconomic metabolism and region development.

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2 Research Questions

This chapter presents the basic research questions for the development of the bioeconomy tool, with a focus on climate change.

- **Research Questions (RQ)**

RQ1. Why is bioeconomy important for Climate Change?

RQ2. Why is the mitigation of Climate Change for Bioeconomy important?

RQ3. Why is a Decision Support Tool in Bioeconomy vs Climate Change important?

RQ4. What is the framework of the Support Decision Tool to boost Bioeconomy and improve its resilience to Climate Change?

- **Addressed Answers**

RQ1. “The bioeconomy covers all sectors and systems that rely on biological resources (animals, plants, micro-organisms and derived biomass, including organic waste), their functions and principles.” (1) with impact on type of land use, biodiversity, carbon and water life cycle, forest/rural fires, resilience for adverse climates and extreme weather events.

(1) Source: Statement on the bioeconomy’s coverage - 2018 revision of the EU’s Bioeconomy Strategy, https://ec.europa.eu/research/bioeconomy/pdf/ec_bioeconomy_strategy_2018.pdf

RQ2. ‘Exploiting biomass is not necessarily circular and sustainable.’ The EU concept of the bioeconomy focuses on

- (1) added value,
- (2) Innovation, and
- (3) Sustainable development.

Added value to prevent the abandonment of economic activity with impact in the mitigation of forest/rural fires;

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Innovation to increase the bioeconomy potential and resilience (climate change and negative demographic evolution from rural to urban region) and the competitiveness to fossil-derived products towards a biobased society; and

Sustainable development to promote (1) the rural development and jobs, (2) the circularity and efficiency in the use of resources, (3) the reduction of GHG emissions, and promote the sequestration and storage of carbon in biomass and soils, (4) land use, (5) biodiversity, and (6) water life cycle.

RQ3. We can use a Bioeconomy like a partner in the fight against climate change. However, this partnership is extremely complex, with different options, pathways, value chains and decision variables.

We don't want the optimum solution.

We want the best possible solution.

Decision support tools are tools designed to help users make more effective decisions by presenting the likelihood of various outcomes resulting from different policies and actions.

RQ4. Decision Support Tool Framework to sustain and help in the increase of the resilience of Bioeconomy to Climate Change (Figures 1.2 and 1.3).

To be an effective decision support tool, it is very important to be able to have a final quantitative assessment, aggregated into a single number and not into a set of numbers and variables (a problem with many decision support tools), meaning that will be specifically presented the best possible solution. Therefore, the mathematical calculation model for this purpose, must be a determinant of an algebraic ratio and not a set of several numbers as the final result. The optimisation of decision support tools is based on pilot implementation tests to verify their functionality and coherence. The definition and selection of principles, criteria and indicators are one of the fundamental bases of a decision support tool, particularly when applying the Multi-criteria Decision Analysis and Life Cycle Assessment methodologies. For this definition, it is important to consider the type of natural resources in focus and the levels of biophysical impact (Figure 2.2). For example, in terms of the Carbon life cycle and impact assessment of a given bioeconomy scenario, on the impact of the global Carbon life cycle balance, from atmospheric capture (level 3 > 0 meters), to stock in trees (level 2 = 0 meters) and stock in the soil (level 1 < 0 meters, due, for example, the type of soil mobilization practices influence the carbon stock in the soil), it is very important to define the intended and considered levels of biophysical impact.

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Framework Bioeconomy Tool

Figure 2.1 Framework of the Bioeconomy Tool.

Framework Bioeconomy Tool: natural resources and biophysical impact

	Type of Resources		Biophysical impact
Air	Level 3	Level > 0 meters	Level 3
Water	Level 2	Level = 0 meters	Level 2
Soil	Level 1	Level < 0 meters	Level 1

Figure 2.2 Type of natural resources and biophysical impact applied to the definition of principles, criteria and indicators, functional unit and boundary systems of the tool.

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3 Bioeconomy tool design

This chapter presents the initial design of the decision support tool applied to the sustainable bioeconomy for the Resist project, with a view to applying it at the meso-scale, i.e. the regional level.

3.1 Problem definition: Sustainable use of resources and the Bioeconomy

In the coming decades, the world will witness increased competition for limited and finite natural resources: over the way land occupation is taking place and the efficiency and necessity of resource utilisation. The growing world population (approaching 9 billion by 2050) is putting additional pressure on the food sector and the use of natural resources, where biosecurity and land use efficiency are key issues (Sheppard et al., 2011). The EU will need renewable biological resources for safe and healthy food and feed, as well as materials, energy and other products. Resource utilisation and the environment (in particular climate change) will have an impact on primary production systems such as forestry, agriculture, fisheries and aquaculture (Thomas et al., 2014; Correll et al., 2014). The European Commission has taken, in 2012, a strategic position to change the European economy towards a more efficient and sustainable use of renewable bioresources (EC, 2012). European ecosystems grow in a wide and diverse range of ecological conditions, from the boreal regions to the Mediterranean and from the alpine regions to the lowlands (FAO, 2010). Ecosystems have been influenced by human settlement and action over the centuries, and in some countries, forest plantations constitute a very important part of existing resources (Raghu et al., 2011).

The sustainable use of resources is essential for most of the world's economic regions to move towards a bioeconomy, as it is one of the main natural resources with the greatest renewable capacity, and sustainable development strategies must be developed (Korhonen, 2004). The Oslo Conference stressed the need to raise awareness of the role of resource exploitation and use in the process of transition to the bioeconomy, recognising the importance of their economic functions and contribution to rural development, enabling the competitiveness of bioeconomy industries (Sheppard et al., 2011).

The development of the bioeconomy could be strategic for the sustainable use of resources, due to its efficiency of use and the dynamisation of new and more competitive value chains, enabling a greater balance in the markets. All the actors generally support the definition of the bioeconomy (bio-based economy) set out in the Commission's reference document (EC, 2011 and EC, 2013a); "[...] a chain of less waste production from the use of land and sea, through the transformation and production of bio-based products adapted to the needs of end users. More precisely, a bio-based economy that integrates the range of natural and renewable biological resources - land and sea resources, biodiversity and biological materials (plant, animal and microbial), through the processing

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and consumption of these biological resources. The bioeconomy covers forestry, agriculture, fisheries, the food and biotechnology sectors, as well as a wide range of industrial sectors (except the use of biotechnology in the medical/pharmaceutical sector), ranging from energy generation and chemical manufacturing to construction and transport. It comprises a wide range of specific and generic technological solutions (already available or yet to be developed), which could be applied in all these sectors to enable sustainable growth and development, for example in terms of safety and the requirements for industrial material for future generations of food."

The bioeconomy includes primary production, such as forestry, agriculture, fisheries and aquaculture, and industries that use/process biological resources, such as the wood products, food and pulp and paper processing industries and part of the chemical, biotechnology and energy industries (Becker et al., 2009). The bioeconomy represents a market estimated at more than 2 trillion euros, providing 20 million jobs and accounting for 9 per cent of total employment in the EU in 2009 (EC, 2014). It is estimated that bio-waste (around 138 million tonnes per year in the EU, of which up to 40% is landfilled) has high added value and potential as a raw material for other production processes (EC, 2014).

The EU also recognises that, due to its transversal nature, the bioeconomy: is an opportunity for economic growth and to solve complex problems; makes it possible to increase the efficiency of use and provision of resources, particularly forest resources, to meet needs; makes it possible to resist and combat climate and societal changes; promotes the development of new value chains, defining market and exploitation quotas based on integrated value cascades at the level of sustainability (EC, 2014; Becker et al., 2009). The different sectors of the bioeconomy have significant impacts on the EU economy, thus representing the need to develop mechanisms and criteria that can reconcile the different economic activities and maximise the benefits of ecosystems (Ragwitz et al., 2009). However, in order for these benefits to be provided and maintained in a balanced way, it is essential to guarantee the sustainable management of resources to enable the sustainable development of the bioeconomy.

- **Sustainability**

Sustainability has turned out to be a challenging concept to measure with traditional tools and methods (Hector et al., 2009; Kunsch et al., 2009). Optimisation methods have been used in sustainability assessments, but in most cases the focus is on maximising profits and other aspects of sustainability are used as constraints (Eid et al., 2002).

Sustainable impact assessment is an approach to exploring the combined impacts of the environmental, economic and social dimensions of a series of proposed policies, programmes, strategies and action plans of a natural or legal person. These assessments can also assist decision-making and strategic planning throughout the policy or production cycle. In its most mature and ambitious form, this evaluation consists of a closed-loop process cycle involving monitoring,

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adaptation and evaluation (using progress indicators). These steps indicate a logical sequence, but as a sustainable impact assessment is not a linear process, cycles of analysis and debate are also involved (OECD, 2010). This assessment should follow a sequence of steps, namely:

1. Screening the proposal: deciding whether an impact assessment is necessary;
2. Scope of the evaluation: decide the extent of the evaluation to be conducted;
3. Select the tools or methodologies to coincide with the definition of the scope;
4. Ensuring stakeholder participation: deciding what the role of stakeholders is, what their interference is in weighing up the evaluation system and framing them according to the intended scope and level;
5. Analysing the environmental, economic and social impacts;
6. Identify the synergies, conflicts and trade-offs between these impacts;
7. Propose mitigating measures to optimise positive results; and
8. Present the results and options to political decision-makers.

The main sustainability impact assessment tools used are presented in Table 3.1., (OECD, 2012b):

- Environment: life cycle assessment, mass and material flows, resource accounting and ecological footprint;
- Economics: cost-benefit analysis, modelling, regression and scenarios; and
- Social: sustainable livelihoods, measuring human and social capital and participatory processes.

Table 3.1 Sustainability assessment tools

Physical assessment tools	Multi-criteria analysis
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Material flow analysis for the whole economy - Life cycle assessment - Ecological footprint - Accounting for global land use / Accounting for total use of emerging resources - National accounting matrix, including the environmental dimension - Characterisation of lifestyle and resource consumption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multi Attribute Value Theory - Weighted sum - Analytical hierarchy process - Regime - Organisational preference ranking method for enrichment evaluations - New approach for imprecise evaluation and decision environments - Dominant method
Monetary valuation tools	Sustainability assessment tools

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cost-benefit analysis - Cost-effectiveness analysis - Measures of economic well-being - Sustainable wellbeing index - Genuine savings - Sustainable national income 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustainable impact assessment - Strategic environmental assessment - Vulnerability assessment 	
Modelling tools		Stakeholder analysis tools	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Climate models - Hydrological models - Biogeochemical models - General economic models - Partial economic sector models - Demographic models - Public health models - Land use models - Integrated assessment models - Qualitative systems analysis - Scenario building and planning tools 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consensus conference - Working group - Repertoire networking technique - "Backcasting": having the future vision of what you want and questioning and planning today what you have to do - Electronic working group - Tools for communicating debates, dialogues and deliberations 	
Scenario analysis - application		Transition management	
Scenario analysis - developing new scenarios			

The need has been recognised, identifying the development of a comprehensive framework of sustainability criteria that focus on the performance of the industrial sector and, more specifically, the assessment of the sustainability of companies. Dozens of indicators have been suggested for use in determining improvements made to processes, a manufacturing site, or a company (Sikdar, 2003). Important developments for sustainability reporting have been the founding of the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD, 1997), the founding of the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI, 2002) and the development of standards for environmental management systems, such as ISO 14000 and EMAS (OECD, 2001). However, in many of the assessment indicator frameworks no attempt has been made to create an aggregate measure to facilitate comparison, for example to assess the development of value chains that use a composite index to give simplified and quantified information on their sustainability performance. In recent years, international research has centred on the development of composite indicators mainly for comparisons between countries on the environmental, economic and social and/or sustainable progress of nations in a quantitative way. These indicators have been applied in a wide variety of fields of application, such as:

- Environment: pilot environmental performance index (WEF, 2002), the environmental friendliness index (Statistics Finland, 2003), eco-indicator 99 (Pre Consultores, 2001);

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- Economy: internal market index (JRC, 2002), composite leading indicators (OECD, 2012a), the index of economic and sustainable well-being (Daly and Cobb, 1989);
- Social: human development index (UNDP, 1990-2003), overall health system performance (Murray et al., 2001); and
- Sustainability: "Dow Jones Sustainability Index" (DJSI, 2003), the index of sustainable balanced development (SELJAK, 2001).

The notion of maximum sustainable yield is based on a model of biological growth (Faucheux and Noël, 1995): it is the idea that, for any population below a certain level K , there is a surplus that can be raised in perpetuity without changing the level of stocks. If this surplus is not raised, stocks will grow to K , which represents the maximum carrying capacity, i.e. the level at which the surplus tends towards 0. The maximum sustainable yield (MSY), on the other hand, corresponds to the point at which the withdrawable surplus is maximised. This is a maximum yield calculated in the absence of any actual harvesting and therefore dependent solely on the biological characteristics of the population. The surplus produced is represented by a parabolic curve $G(x)$ (Faucheux and Noël, 1995). Figure 3.1. shows on the (y,x) plane the curve $y = G(x)$ representing this surplus, with the characteristic values K and x_{RMS} of the population and the surplus RMS.

Figure 3.1. Maximum load capacity and maximum sustainable yield (Faucheux and Noël, 1995).

Despite the significant number of indicators and methodologies that have been developed, there is still no useful and simple method for assessing the integrated sustainability of forest ecosystems on a global scale. In order to meet the challenges of sustainability, an approach to integrated assessment models of the value chains of exploitation and management of the forest territory is needed, which will enable correct guidance for decision-making. It has been foreseen that the

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aggregation of indicators can provide an opportunity for new policy instruments and better integration of decision-making, as well as public participation in the discussion of guiding sustainability. It is also clear that the methods for aggregating indicators are either not sufficiently well established, are under development, or are not available with regard to all aspects and considerations of sustainability and the multiplicity associated with the different territories that exist on a global scale.

The use of decision support tools in controlled and closed contexts (e.g. application to the optimisation of an industrial process) allows for greater reliability and control of the results. The model presented in this document, in terms of its methodology, has advantages over other models because it makes it possible to apply the concept of sustainability assessment on a global scale without distorting the concept given the creation of the term "sustainability" at the United Nations Conference in 1972: the sustainable use of natural resources must "meet the needs of the present generation without affecting the ability of future generations to meet theirs", and there is the same importance for all decision variables. However, when sustainability assessment is carried out and decision support models are applied on a global scale, it involves gathering information and data based on available articles and studies, which can contain distorted information because they are sometimes very dependent on the information that stakeholders provide. These, in turn, represent lobbies and specific intentions. In addition, there are few studies by different authors for the same process, which leads to greater uncertainty when calculating an integrated sustainability index for different modelled scenarios. This section (3) presents a new approach, based on the development of a new decision support tool for integrated sustainability assessment applied to the Bioeconomy.

Environment

In environmental terms, the history of natural disturbances should be an important consideration when choosing a bioeconomy system. Hurricanes, fires, diseases, droughts and grazing by native herbivores are just some of the natural events that have shaped the composition and structure of ecosystems over time. The rate at which these events have historically occurred can vary greatly from regular (for minor disturbances) to highly variable (for major catastrophic disturbances) (Davis et al., 2001).

Economy

The bioeconomy analyses bio-resources from the perspective of maximising the effective benefit for people. This benefit is analysed from two perspectives: the micro perspective (company) and the macro perspective (regions and nations). The microeconomic perspective analyses the individual benefits of the company and focuses on the accumulation of wealth; the macroeconomic perspective analyses the benefit from the point of view of the economy and focuses on the aggregate measure of "economic health", as well as employment, income and gross national product (Bebbington et al., 2007).

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From an economic point of view, ecosystems should be valued from the perspective that they will produce the greatest net benefit for human beings (Colombo, et al., 2012). We often make this assessment from the point of view of the landowner, leaving the ecological and social perspectives up to them. As the landowner's overall goal is to maximise the Net Present Value (NPV), social and environmental issues are often forgotten and ignored. Maximising a viable return is another economic objective, and is fundamental to both the flow of income and costs over time (Davis, 2001). In the forest sector, the economic metabolism is influenced by the price of the timber. Timber is looked as the main economic product and the economic base line for evaluation processes. This vision influences the management of the forest ecosystem: minimum cost and maximum profit, independently of the management practices. On the cost side, it is hard to beat age management with clear felling for the lowest cost per unit of timber produced, unless regeneration costs become unbearable. Partial felling associated with irregular age management usually means higher logging costs and more roads to build and maintain. On the revenue side, the picture is much less lucid. In many cases, not all species and sizes can be sold. So, clear-cutting can present a position that means more trees are cut than can be economically removed. In such cases, from an economic perspective, you would expect some form of partial felling to be used.

The bioeconomy strategy depends on the feasibility and reasonableness of investing in the exploitation of bio-resources. Externalities, which are interactions outside of commercial exchange, therefore correspond to a lack of property rights over "environmental goods". This can be seen as a return to the idea of the classics, considering, in accordance with the old Roman law concept of "things without owners", air, water, etc., as "free goods", that is, not appropriated, and therefore not economic (Faucheux and Noël, 1995). It is important to consider and evaluate which value chains give rise to the least externalities, as these are costs not incurred in the balance of trade but which have a significant impact on some regions and countries. If we abandon the idea of the internationalisation of the externality, which represents pollution or damage, on a microeconomic basis, standard economic analysis can also lead to the development of methods for evaluating the gains (conceived as avoided damage) resulting from correct policies and measures (Faucheux and Noël, 1995). As far as the valuation of environmental goods and services is concerned, their non-commercial nature, and therefore the absence of a market price, makes their monetary valuation difficult a priori.

Social

From a social point of view, the aim is for a bioeconomy system that provides the highest level of social welfare. The main considerations may be the local and skilled employment provided by the system, the cultural significance of different systems, among others. Community stability in rural areas can be partly attributed to the collection of bioresources and associated employment, but the quality of leisure opportunities is also important to the public (Davis et al., 2001). A concept called

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"social acceptability" can be a vehicle for aggregating these distinct factors in terms of the public's view of different bioeconomic systems.

3.2 Multifunctional bioeconomy pilot region: a tool for Climate Change fight

As society raises concerns with environmental responsibility from businesses and suppliers increases, and as policy makers evaluate more complex scenarios to prevent environmental catastrophes, it is increasingly important to address climate change issues related to socio-economic development. The circular and sustainable bioeconomy is one of these proposed development trajectories with impact in the three important dimensions of the climate change: "AIR", "LAND" and "WATER". Additionally, a resilient and safe environment are a key option to integrate with circular and sustainable dimension for the Climate Change fight.

A Portuguese pilot is focused in an agroforest socioeconomic metabolism and region, with a strategic intervention objective:

- Development of a new bioeconomy approach (a tool) with 4 level functions in response to climate change:
 - o Circular (increase the lifetime and the efficiency use of the bioresources; reuse and recycle materials throughout the value chain);
 - o Sustainable (resource management – responsible use of shared and consumption of resources; upgrade residues and waste to higher value products and ecosystem services to optimize the quality and value of biomass; capacity to create new and high qualified jobs; provide rural areas with environmental, social and economic opportunities and encourage new partnerships – at local, regional, national and global levels; develop and share financially viable and sustainable business models; provide scientific and technological R&D infrastructures; facilitates the reuse, recycling and upcycling of bio-based products; encourage green procurement in both the public and private sectors; commit to education and awareness of sustainable practices from early schools levels through university);
 - o Resilient (value the biodiversity and genetic knowledge & new silviculture models against the rural/forest fires, hydric stress and phytosanitary problems that are increasing with the climate change; resilient and diverse ecosystems – a habitable planet; support and promote actions to and refine alternatives to fossil-based products and processes); and

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- Safe (security byproducts; no competition with agrifood sector; preserve the land and resources; security of human zones against rural/forest fires and floods, caused by storms).
- Management of the fuel availability in agroforest ecosystem by a (1) new planning and governance mechanism to economic viable biomass collection and (2) increase the value and efficiency process use of biomass based on Integrated Biorefinery (production of fine chemicals, biobased materials and advanced biofuels, based on cascade use principles).
- Cross strategies models for prevent Climate Change: Evolutionary models and plant material of forest resilience to climate change applicable to Central and Northern Europe, based on the knowledge and genetic heritage of resilience from southern Europe (forecast and anticipatory approaches to the problems caused by the temperature growth: water stress, plant health and rural/forest fires). Will be performed climate resilience tests (controlled greenhouse, with digital twins' technology) and the introduction of hydric, thermal, phytosanitary stress factors to induce and develop plants with greater resilience.

Bioeconomy Tool Outputs:

- Modulation of the Tool to support the transition to a multifunction Bioeconomy pilot region;
- Design and implement new policies, support the government model for the planning, management and decision-making of bioresources with an impact on rural/forest fires (biomass from marginal lands and agroforestry residues) and the development of the “co-economy” (based on forest by-products);
- Silviculture model for prevention of erosion and lixiviation of the mountain soils (use the structure and type of the plant as a tool);
- High value biobased products produced in a biorefinery pilot presenting in the region (multi supply framework of bioresources from forest and marginal land ecosystem based on residues and raw materials that not represent deforestation);
- Genetic map of the best performance plant against to hydric stress and phytosanitary problems; and
- Molecular Biology vs Plant Health vs Preventing: modeling and anticipating profiles of climate change in the region in Northern Europe through models of knowledge and molecular evolution of plants in Southern Europe (first zone to suffer effects of climate change in Europe) of phytosanitary (carry out simulation tests of existing phytosanitary pathogen

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migrations in southern Europe to predict what might happen in northern Europe with climate change), hydric and temperature resilience.

3.3 Design the Bioeconomy Resist tool

Highlights:

- 1) it integrates the principles defined for sustainability, i.e. it does not distort the definition and basic standards, integrating the conservation and defense of the functions of ecosystems without forgetting that for the development of society the social and economic dimension must also be taken into account;
- 2) it has the potential to assess the value chains for the use of ecosystem resources on a global scale. It allows for an assessment between chains or systems in any territory, by integrating the criteria and indicators of certification schemes in operation and the most important standards and directives linked to sustainability, sustainable management and international trade; and
- 3) makes it possible to quantify the degree of sustainability of a given value chain throughout its entire life cycle, proposing the use of a resulting sustainability vector, specifically a composite index. Sustainability is defined by a triangle made up of the environmental, social and economic vectors, where it is stated that each of the vectors is equally important when analyzing and assessing the sustainability of any system, process or material. In this way, the triangle is equilateral. Figure 3.2 shows the triangle of the sustainability principle with the environmental, social and economic weight vectors identified, as well as the weight vector resulting from the central convex combination of the objective functions.

Mathematical model applied

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Figure 3.2. Illustration of the resulting weight vector applied to the "Sustainability Triangle".

The model designed defines environmental, economic and social indicators as a group of indicators, associated in sub-indices of sustainability and, finally, in a general index of sustainable performance. In order to develop the model and the Integrated Sustainability Assessment Index on a Global Scale, $I_{BioS,t}$ at time (year) t , which allows the impact on a global scale to be determined, it is necessary to use the principles of the "Analytic Hierarchy Process, AHP" and "Multi-Attribute Utility Theory, MAUT" methods. Using AHP, it is possible to introduce qualitative and quantitative criteria in a multi-level model (hierarchical structure). With MAUT, a direct classification is made, assigning numerical values proportional to their importance, allowing each alternative to be evaluated in relation to each decision criterion through relative numerical values that reflect their priorities. The integration of the Life Cycle Assessment procedure and approach through the ISO 14040-44:2006 standards stipulates that before calculating the $I_{BioS,t}$, (1) the scope and objective of the study, (2) the functional unit, value chains and system boundary, (3) and the life cycle inventory are defined, with identification of the sources of information and data quality. The model uses standardized environmental, economic and social indicators to incorporate them into a single performance measure.

Figure 3.3. shows the $I_{BioS,t}$ calculation structure based on a hierarchy and with the integration of the normalization and dimensioning of the different types of indicators.

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Figure 3.3. Generic hierarchical structure for calculating $I_{BioS,t}$.

Mendoza et al. (1989) defined the first hierarchical structure for measuring sustainability, consisting of 4 levels. The first level is the principles, followed by the criteria, then the indicators and finally the verifiers (Mendoza and Prabhu 2000a and 2003). The model uses only three levels, down to the indicators, so as not to make the model too complex, as it is intended to be used on a global scale. The composite sustainability assessment index $I_{BioS,t}$ is made up of a combination of sub-indices (Eq. 3.1.) and represents the main basis of the Bioeconomy tool.

$$I_{BioS,t} = \sum_{jt}^n W_j SI_{jt} \quad (3.1)$$

where W_j indicates the weight factor that represents a given priority for group j of n sustainable development indicators. The weights reflect the importance given to the environmental, economic and social performance of the bioeconomy value chain to be assessed. These weights, according to the Sustainability Triangle (Figure 3.2), have the same priority, i.e. as there are 3 groups of indicators, this means that $W_1 = 0.33$, $W_2 = 0.33$ and $W_3 = 0.33$. Calculating the $I_{BioS,t}$ is a step-by-step procedure that groups several basic indicators into a sustainability sub-index (SI_{jt}) for each group of sustainability indicators j . The sub-indices can be derived as shown in Equations 3.2. and 3.3.

$$SI_{jt} = \sum_{jit}^n W_{ij} I_{N,jit} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\sum_{ji}^n W_{ij} = 1, \quad W_{ij} \geq 0 \text{ e } W_{ij} = \frac{1}{n} \quad (3.3)$$

where:

- Sl_{jt} is the sustainability sub-index for a set of j indicators (environmental, $j = 1$, economic, $j = 2$ and social, $j = 3$) at time (year) t .
- W_{ij} is the weight of indicator i for the group of sustainability indicators j and reflects the importance of this indicator in assessing the sustainability of the forest ecosystem value chain, so that each indicator has the same weight of importance as defined. However, the tool is adapted for use in other types of situations, such as defining internal company strategies.

The main problem with aggregating indicators for $I_{BioS,t}$ is the fact that indicators can be expressed in different units (e.g. $kgCO_{2eq}$, MJ or number of jobs). One way to solve this problem is to normalize each indicator i (Eq. 3.4.) by dividing its value at time (year) t by a higher target $I_{max,jt}$ and $I_{min,jt}$.

$$I_{N,ijt} = \frac{I_{A,ijt} - I_{min,jt}}{I_{max,jt} - I_{min,jt}} \times 100 \quad (3.4)$$

Where IN_{ijt} is the standardized indicator i for the group of indicators j for time (year) t , $I_{A,ijt}$ is the non-standardized evaluation indicator i for the group of indicators j for time (year) t , $I_{max,jt}$ is the upper target defined as the value sufficient to guarantee maximum satisfaction of indicator i (it can be the highest or lowest numerical value, depending on the type of indicator), and $I_{min,jt}$ is the lower target defined. This procedure allows for simplification and analysis on a global scale, without making an iterative procedure too long and without the possibility of knowing at a given moment in time (year) t on a global scale what the maximum or minimum possible performance value is for an indicator i in a group of indicators j . In this way, it is only necessary to define the maximum that should be achieved and the minimum threshold that defines that below this value all performances are considered zero, due to their insufficient performance.

The Bioeconomy tool thus defines two thresholds, a lower one (Eq. 3.5) and an upper one (Eq. 3.6) where:

$$\text{If } I_{A,ijt} < I_{min,jt}, \text{ then } I_{A,ijt} = I_{min,jt} \quad (3.5)$$

$$\text{If } I_{A,ijt} > I_{max,jt}, \text{ then } I_{A,ijt} = I_{max,jt} \quad (3.6)$$

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considering the groups of indicators and indicators in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2 Groups of indicators and indicators do $I_{BioS,t}$

Groups of indicators	Notation Group, j	Indicators
Environment	1	$I_{A,1i}, i = 1, \dots, n$
Economic	2	$I_{A,2i}, i = 1, \dots, n$
Social	3	$I_{A,3i}, i = 1, \dots, n$

The two thresholds can be defined in political terms, either at national or global level, and can result from a political or technical-scientific understanding. The Bioeconomy tool can also be applied to a business context. It is therefore a dynamic sustainability assessment tool. It has the possibility of incorporating different types of quantities, with different units of measurement (i.e. physical, economic, etc.). One of the advantages of the proposed standardization of indicators is the clear compatibility of different indicators, since all the indicators are standardized. The model developed makes it possible to compare two value chains from two different ecosystems (A1 and B1) and from two different geographical regions (R1 and R2) (see Figure 3.4.). The normalization of the indicators on a scale of 0 to 100, with the definition of the upper and lower threshold, simplifies the evaluation process and makes it more feasible, because you are not always looking for the best value that could exist for indicator I_{ij} . The example in Figure 3.4. shows that I_{ij} in the CVB1 value chain is higher than the defined threshold. Using the model developed, a score of 100 is obtained, resulting from the normalization process defined in the previous equations.

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Figure 3.4. Example of the interpretation of the model developed and the simplification of standardization and evaluation for application on a global scale.

This procedure for defining LS and LI makes it possible to simplify the process and consequently apply it on a global scale. It can also be applied in a business context, where the company defines the maximum and minimum limits for each indicator.

This results in the development of a decision-support tool for managing forest ecosystems, through the application of an integrated and global sustainability assessment index, with the capacity to adapt to different contexts (global and individual). In addition, it is important to note that the principles for assigning weights defined in the equation make it possible to comply with the rules and standards defined by the WTO.

The calculation model developed will be applied in this project taking into account the principles of sustainability and bioeconomy, i.e. each indicator and group of indicators takes on the same priority. However, the Bioeconomy calculation model is a powerful tool that can be applied in other sustainability assessment contexts. A given process, system or value chain is considered sustainable if the $I_{BioS,t}$ is greater than or equal to 50.

Indicators: sustainable development

The review of the scientific literature permitted to identify the environment, economic and social indicators to support and promotion the Sustainable Development of the Bioeconomy to apply at region level (Table 3.3 summarize the review performed).

Table 3.3 Review of the indicators of sustainability

Indicators	Rationale	Sustainability Dimension	Source
Sustainability threshold levels for Bioeconomy Technologies	New indicator based on genuine investment theory with a focus on the bio-based economy	Environment	Bartolini et al., 2017; Wesseler et al., 2007
Biodiversity	Indispensable to assess the impact of biomass production at the genetic, species, and ecosystem level	Environment	SAT-BBE, 2018; Bartolini et al., 2017; Plieninger et al., 2019; Strohbach et al., 2015; Weikard et al., 2006
Land cover	To assess land use conflict	Environment	Lier et al., 2018

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Biomass availability	Addresses issue of sustainability and is ambiguous about source of supply	Environment	BERST, 2016
Land use	Land use for primary biomass purposes most relevant to bioeconomy suitability	Environment	BERST, 2016
Resource use efficiency		Environment	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Energy efficiency		Environment	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Self-sufficiency of energy supply		Environment	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Land use efficiency		Environment	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Infrastructure	Attractiveness of place is outcome of state of infrastructure; perhaps better than quantitative measure of networks	Environment	BERST, 2016
Sustainable resource use	To assess the sustainability of biomass production	Environment	Lier et al., 2018
Bio-energy replacing non-renewable energy	To assess the direct substitutability of fossil resources with biological resources	Environment	Kardung et al., 2021
Bio-material replacing non-renewable resources	To assess the direct substitutability of fossil resources with biological resources	Environment	Lier et al., 2018
Decoupling from use of fossil resources		Environment	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Certified bio-based products	To assess the variety of products from bio-based production.	Environment	Kardung et al., 2021
Greenhouse gas emissions	Traditional indicator applied to bioeconomy sectors	Environment	EUROSTAT, 2019
Climate footprint	To assess CO2 emissions for sectors based on life cycle assessments of bio-based production	Environment	Kardung et al., 2021
Climate change adaptation	More indicators of adaption to climate change impacts are needed.	Environment	Kardung et al., 2021

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Decarbonization of the industry		Environment	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Cascading factors		Environment	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Waste avoidance and minimization		Environment	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Water use efficiency		Environment	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Eco-design and Circular economy		Environment	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Renewable power and heat		Environment	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Avoidance of persistent, toxic, and bioaccumulating substances		Environment	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Primary Biomass production	To assess biomass availability	Economy	BERST, 2016
Biomass self-sufficiency rate	To assess independence from biomass imports.	Economy	Kardung et al., 2021
Material use efficiency	To assess the degree of circularity	Economy	Lier et al., 2018
Innovation	Traditional indicator applied in more sectorial and spatial detail	Economy	Lier et al., 2018; SAT-BBE, 2018
Investments	To assess biomass flows within the EU between the rest of the world	Economy	Lier et al., 2018; Bartolini et al., 2017
Value Added of the bioeconomy sectors	To assess product uptake of bio-based production	Economy	Lier et al., 2018
Comparative advantage	To assess biomass flows within the EU between the rest of the world	Economy	Kardung et al., 2021
Production and consumption of non-food and feed bio-based products	Traditional indicator applied in more sectorial and spatial detail	Economy	Kardung et al., 2021
Import and export of bioeconomy raw materials and products	To assess biomass flows within the EU between the rest of the world	Economy	Kardung et al., 2021

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Cluster size	Where the number of firms in relevant part of bioeconomy sectors is high it suggests a strong degree of potential clustering. This includes firms in the 'traditional' non-biobased sector as well as bioeconomy firms; the 'traditional' base is key to future development of the sector, particularly in the chemical and energy sectors, as they have the most potential to substitute fossil fuel inputs with bio-based equivalents.	Economy	BERST, 2016
Funding	Role of government in providing funding. Is the key question around availability of funds.	Economy	BERST, 2016
Cluster and regional networking		Socioeconomic	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Competitive products		Socioeconomic	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
R&D employment		Socioeconomic	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Employment of qualified/unskilled workers		Socioeconomic	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Average/Fair Income of employees		Socioeconomic	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Rate of formation of small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) and of start-up companies		Socioeconomic	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Creation of added value		Socioeconomic	Hildebrandt et al., 2020
Bioeconomy-driving Policies	To assess policies, strategies, and legislation on the bioeconomy	Social	Kardung et al., 2021
Availability of food Access to food Utilization Stability	To assess the contribution of the bioeconomy to food and nutrition security based on the widely accepted four dimension of food security	Social	FAO, 2009

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Employment	Traditional indicator applied in more sectorial and spatial detail	Social	Lier et al., 2018
Cluster management	Incubators are likely to lead to more business start-ups and higher survival rates	Social	BERST, 2016
Demographics	Key indicator of demographic movements. Key indicator of size of potential workforce	Social	BERST, 2016
Quality of workforce	More skilled workforce more likely to be able to perform high value-added roles in bioeconomy	Social	BERST, 2016
Policy/ regulation setting	Indicates their willingness to adapt policy/regulation to make business easier for the bioeconomy	Social	BERST, 2016

Next Steps:

- Definition of principles, criteria and indicators;
- Scenario modulation: traditional ad new (biorefinery concept & genetic resistance plant improvement guidelines);
- Implementing and testing;
- Identification of the needs to improve the tool.

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